

An AI Virtual Team of Coordinated Agents for Exploratory Clinical Trial Data Analysis

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Abstract

Background

Exploratory analyses of clinical trial data are essential for generating hypotheses and advancing scientific understanding, but they are resource- and time-intensive, often requiring coordination across multiple experts. Generative AI (GenAI) has the potential to automate key steps in these workflows, reducing operational barriers while expanding the scope of data exploration and uncovering new insights. We hypothesize that a GenAI-based “Virtual Team” can emulate the exploratory analysis process, enhancing efficiency and scientific discovery.

Methods

We developed a Virtual Team composed of three AI agents: a Scientific Agent, a Coding Agent, and a Medical Writing Agent. Each was equipped with detailed metadata on patient-level ADaM datasets and carefully designed system prompts serving as guardrails to ensure appropriate, interpretable outputs. The Scientific Agent generated analysis plans; the Coding Agent produced statistical code, which was run based on individual patient-level data; and the Medical Writing Agent drafted summary reports. Implemented in R and using the OpenAI API (GPT-5), the Virtual Team was evaluated using a phase 1 oncology trial. In response to a general prompt to “*Summarize the dataset focusing on findings that are clinically meaningful.*”, the system was run ten times, each producing ten analyses and a 200-word report. All outputs were reviewed by a human expert.

Results

Each analysis plan covered baseline characteristics, efficacy, and safety domains. These plans were accurately translated into executable statistical code, with minor coding errors automatically detected and re-executed. Across ten runs, 117 unique analytical results were produced (median per report = 39). Core results, such as patient counts and survival estimates, were consistently reproduced across all runs. Other analyses appeared only in a subset of runs, a desirable variability that reflects the Virtual Team’s analytical breadth and flexibility in exploring the data. All reports accurately represented the underlying data and results.

Conclusions

This proof-of-concept demonstrates that a GenAI-based Virtual Team can effectively perform exploratory clinical trial data analyses. The findings highlight a scalable framework for embedding GenAI as an expert companion, broadening the scope and efficiency of clinical data analytics.

Introduction

The comprehensive, high-quality nature of clinical trial data makes them well suited for additional exploration and *post hoc* analyses. [1-2]. Such analyses may uncover novel insights that can accelerate scientific progress and generate new hypotheses.

The process of conducting exploratory analyses based on trial data, however, is resource-intensive and involves multiple stakeholders with diverse expertise. Typical steps include developing an analysis plan, generating statistical code and outputs, and summarizing the findings. These activities can be time-consuming, limiting the ability of experts to focus on the critical task of scientific interpretation. The high workload arises in part from the need to understand both the medical context and the available clinical trial data – knowledge essential to proposing analyses and providing clear instructions to statistical and programming teams. Additional bottlenecks often arise during (1) the translation of analysis proposals into statistical code for clinical trial Analysis Data Model (ADaM) datasets and (2) the translation of statistical results into concise summary reports.

Recently, interest has grown in using Generative AI (GenAI) to build Virtual Teams that accelerate scientific work. For example, the Microsoft AI team has applied AI agents to tackle complex medical diagnostic challenges, with agents working sequentially to investigate clinical problems [3]. Similarly, a GenAI-based Virtual Lab was developed to perform interdisciplinary research, successfully applied to the design of new SARS-CoV-2 nanobodies [4]. Within the pharmaceutical industry, early initiatives are also exploring GenAI solutions that generate Tables, Listings and Figures (TLFs) and that generate various draft reports [5-8].

Beyond improving efficiency, GenAI also has the potential to broaden the scope of scientific exploration. By rapidly generating and testing diverse analytical ideas, GenAI systems can propose alternative or complementary analyses that may differ from those envisioned by human teams. Such perspectives can stimulate new lines of inquiry, foster creative scientific thinking, and ultimately lead to a deeper and more holistic understanding of clinical data.

Despite these promising developments, no existing solutions address the unique challenges of exploratory clinical trial data analysis, where medical and statistical expertise must be seamlessly integrated. To fill this gap, we developed a GenAI-based Virtual Team and hypothesized that it could automate the full analytical cycle: (1) generating an analysis plan, (2) producing and executing statistical code, and (3) summarizing results for interpretation. We evaluated this hypothesis using data from a phase 1 oncology trial, with expert review of the resulting outputs including the statistical code and draft summary reports. By reducing the operational burden of routine tasks, the Virtual Team aims to free clinical trial experts to focus on scientific reasoning and hypothesis generation, thereby augmenting discovery from high-quality trial data.

Methods

Data

We used data from a phase 1 oncology clinical trial to evaluate the Virtual Team's performance. The data followed the Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC) ADaM standard, which is the regulatory-accepted format for clinical trial analyses. The ADaM package consisted of multiple domains (separate datasets), of which we focused on four that capture the most critical clinical information typically included in oncology summary reports:

- **ADSL** (subject-level data): one row per patient.
- **ADRS** (clinical response assessments): CDISC basic data structure; one row per patient per response parameter per visit.
- **ADTTE** (time-to-event data): CDISC basic data structure; one row per patient per endpoint, such as overall survival.
- **ADAE** (safety data): CDISC occurrence structure; one row per patient per adverse event.

These datasets together provide a comprehensive view of baseline characteristics, efficacy outcomes, and safety information. Dataset sizes varied, with some containing over 2,000 rows and more than 100 columns, reflecting the typical complexity of oncology trial data.

The data were used solely to demonstrate the methodology. No clinical conclusions were drawn from these analyses, and the results shown are illustrative only. Figures in this manuscript display synthetic or illustrative outputs.

Implementation

The Virtual Team was set up using R (version 4.4.1). The OpenAI Application Programming Interface (API) was used via an enterprise account. A convenient R function (`vteam_act`) was developed to run the Virtual Team.

Workflow and AI agents

Figure 1 illustrates the workflow of the AI Virtual Team. The system is built around three sequential agents, with the output of each agent appended to the input of the next. The process begins with a starting prompt, which is passed as input to the Scientific Agent.

Figure 2 illustrates the role of each agent and provides example output. Each agent has been tailored through carefully designed system prompts. In addition, all three agents are provided with detailed trial metadata, including dataset names, column names and labels, variable names, and possible cell values. The metadata enable the agents to perform their roles effectively: (1) build an analysis plan, (2) write executable code, and (3) summarize results.

- **Scientific Agent** defines the analysis plan. This plan consists of specific analysis proposals, each explicitly linked to relevant datasets, variables, and parameters.

- **Coding Agent** generates R code for each proposed analysis. A separate agent call is made for each analysis. The resulting R scripts are then executed in a computing environment resulting in statistical outputs.
- **Medical Writing Agent** summarizes the statistical outputs into a narrative report.

The complete output of the workflow is returned to the user as an R list, which contains the key components: (1) the analysis plan, (2) the code/script for each analysis, (3) the results of each analysis, and (4) the final summary report.

R code execution

Each R script generated by the Virtual Team is automatically executed on individual patient-level ADaM data. To prevent interruptions, execution is wrapped in a safe evaluation function that quietly returns a fallback value (NA) if an error occurs, rather than halting the process. In such cases, the system then automatically generates revised code tailored to the specific analysis and re-runs it. This two-step safeguard protects against common GenAI-based coding errors – such as misspelled variable names or incorrect package calls – that could otherwise result in incomplete summary reports.

Application and evaluation of the AI Virtual Team

We then applied the Virtual Team to the oncology phase 1 clinical trial data using the following specifications:

- **Starting prompt:** *Summarize the dataset focusing on findings that are clinically meaningful.*
- **GenAI model:** GPT-5
- **ADaM datasets in scope for the analysis:** ADSL, ADRS, ADTTE, ADAE
- **Number of analyses:** 10
- **Approximate word count report:** 200

To evaluate performance, the procedure was repeated ten times, and a human expert reviewed all Virtual Team-generated outputs and reports for accuracy and quality.

Reproducibility

Implementation code for the AI Virtual Team is publicly available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17661870>). Synthetic data are provided to demonstrate functionality.

Results

Although the starting prompt in our experiment was broad (“*Summarize the dataset focusing on findings that are clinically meaningful.*”), in all runs, the Virtual Team addressed all key data domains: patient characteristics, clinical response assessments, time-to-event outcomes, and adverse events. Every analysis plan included at least one analysis for each of these four domains. All proposed analyses were judged to be meaningful, clinically relevant, and statistically sound.

All 100 R scripts generated by the Virtual Team (ten analyses for each of ten reports) ultimately produced accurate, executable statistical code (**Figure 3A**). In four instances, the initial version of the code did not execute successfully due to minor errors – two involving non-existent variables, one a misspelled dataset name, and one incorrect package usage (`stats::summary()` vs `survival::summary()`). In each case, the system automatically generated a corrected version that executed successfully on the subsequent attempt.

Across the ten runs, the Virtual Team generated a total of 117 unique analytical results, which were included in the ten 200-word reports. An analytical result was defined as any count, percentage, model estimate, or confidence interval bound (explaining why a single R script could yield more than one result). All 117 results were accurate and correctly described in the reports, which were deemed readily interpretable by the human expert reviewer.

The median number of analytical results included in a report was 39 (range: 31–54). Most results appeared only once or few times across the ten reports; however, a small core set was present in all ten reports: the number of patients in the full analysis set, objective response rate (N subjects and %), complete responders (N subjects and %), median progression-free and overall survival (PFS/OS; Kaplan-Meier estimates with 95% CIs; number of events), and treatment-emergent adverse events of grade 3 or higher (N subjects and %) (**Figure 3B**).

Discussion

We demonstrated that a generative AI-based Virtual Team has the potential to automate meaningful parts of the exploratory clinical trial data analysis workflow, including generating analysis plans, producing executable statistical code, and drafting narrative summaries. Applied repeatedly to oncology trial data, the system consistently proposed clinically relevant analyses, produced executable statistical code, and delivered summaries that were judged accurate by expert review. These findings suggest that GenAI can complement human expertise by reducing the operational workload of data exploration, freeing domain experts to focus on interpretation and hypothesis generation.

Our work extends previous research on the use of GenAI to augment scientific research including the analysis of clinical trial and other human data [3-8]. Our contribution is domain-specific: we translate the roles of a clinical trial analysis team into multiple coordinated agents that plan, execute, and summarize analyses. Using structured metadata and business rules, the Virtual Team reliably translated high-level requests into analysis plans, executable code, and plain-language reports. This mimics established workflows in clinical research but accelerates execution and reduces the need for repetitive, manual tasks.

Our evaluation with the broad starting prompt (“*Summarize the dataset focusing on findings that are clinically meaningful.*”) demonstrated that the Virtual Team does not simply return a fixed set of outputs but instead produces a broad spectrum of analytical results from the same data. Across ten runs (and a 200-word report per run), 117 unique results were generated (median number per report = 39), encompassing descriptive summaries and statistical model estimates. While certain core findings (e.g., patient counts, adverse event summaries, and median PFS/OS) were included in all reports, the majority of results were included in only one or few of the reports. This diversity is advantageous – when the goal is to generate novel insights: if the tool had only reproduced the same fixed outputs each time, its contribution would have been limited. Instead, by generating a wide range of analyses, the Virtual Team complements human investigators, inspires alternative perspectives, and has the potential to uncover insights that may otherwise remain hidden.

Another strength of the Virtual Team is its ability to generate effective strategies and executable statistical code even for large and complex datasets. Even for datasets with numerous parameters and multiple timepoints per subject (e.g., ADRS – clinical response assessments), performance was equivalent to simpler datasets (e.g., ADSL – subject-level information).

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, while the generated code in our example executed successfully, some proposals required code to be re-generated as part of a second attempt before running as intended. This highlights the importance of maintaining quality control prior to any clinical decision-making. Second, our evaluation was limited to a single phase 1 oncology trial; broader testing across trial phases and therapeutic areas will be

necessary to establish generalizability. Finally, although the summaries were accurate as draft outputs, they were not designed to replace the nuanced interpretation and contextualization provided by clinical and statistical experts.

Future enhancements for the solution could take several directions. For instance, our team is working on enabling the generation of figures and tables alongside the written summaries. The current system is optimized for R, a common language used for statistical analyses in exploratory clinical research. Future developments could expand compatibility to other languages such as SAS and Python, further broadening its applicability across analytical environments. We also plan to explore broader applications across different trial designs and to apply the Virtual Team to real-world datasets.

Overall, this work illustrates the potential of GenAI to act as a virtual collaborator in clinical trial data exploration. With appropriate governance, such systems may accelerate the generation of insights from trial data and support the development of new hypotheses, complementing the unique expertise of clinical development professionals.

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Consent for publication: Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials: The complete R code as well as synthetic data are available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17661870>).

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Authors' contributions: MG conceptualized and designed the study, implemented the AI Virtual Team, performed all analyses, and drafted the manuscript. All authors contributed to the interpretation of results, provided critical revisions, and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Figures and tables

Figure 1. Schematic of the AI Virtual Team

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Note:

- Each agent is provided with detailed trial metadata and carefully designed system prompts.
- The agents run sequentially; the output from each agent is appended to the next agent's input prompt.
- The dashed line indicates that the system can be rerun to implement requested updates.
- The starting prompt may range from a general description of the desired outcome to a detailed, predefined template that outlines the specific analyses and outputs required.

Figure 2. Details of the three coordinated agents

<p>1. Scientific Agent</p> <p>Task: Develop analysis plan</p> <p>System message: <i>You are a scientist who understands clinical trial ADaM data. Propose exactly 10 [number to be set by user] straightforward analyses that summarize the clinical trial...</i></p> <p>Example output</p> <p>n1: In ADSL, count USUBJID where FASFL = 'Y' to derive the number of subjects in the full analysis set.</p> <p>n2: Kaplan-Meier estimate of median AVAL for PARAM = 'Overall Survival (months)' in ADEFFTE for USUBJID in ADSL with FASFL = 'Y', using AVAL and event indicator (1 - CNSR)</p> <p>...</p>	<p>3. Medical Writing Agent</p> <p>Task: Generate plain-text summary of statistical results</p> <p>System message: <i>You are a medical writer specialized in clinical data reporting. Your task is to summarize analytical results - without interpretation or contextual commentary - for a general scientific/clinical audience...</i></p> <p>Example output</p> <p>The Full Analysis Set included 101 subjects with a median age of 69 years (range 23–85). Baseline ECOG performance status was 0 in 37 subjects (36.7%), 1 in 50 (49.5%), and 2 in 14 (13.9%).</p> <p>By Investigator Lugano Criteria at the endpoint, the objective response rate was 60.3% (61/101), including a complete response rate of 51.5% (52/101) and a disease control rate of 57.4% (58/101).</p> <p>Median progression-free survival was 5.28 months (95% CI 3.18–6.24) based on 66 events and 35 censored observations. Median overall survival was 21.4 months (95% CI 13.5–29.9) with 52 deaths and 49 censored. Among responders (n=61), the median duration of response was 25.1 months (95% CI 15.4–40.1) with 42 events and 19 censored. Time to next anti-lymphoma therapy was 7.64 months (95% CI 5.89–18.95).</p> <p>Treatment-emergent adverse events of grade 3 or higher occurred in 75 of 101 subjects (74.3%). Cytokine release syndrome occurred in 51 subjects (50.5%). Grade 3 or higher infections were reported in 53 subjects (52.5%). Treatment-emergent adverse events leading to permanent discontinuation occurred in 12 subjects (11.9%).</p>
<p>2. Coding Agent</p> <p>Task: Write code for each analysis included in the plan, which is subsequently run in SCE</p> <p>System message: <i>You are a statistician or programmer specialized in R programming. Your ENTIRE reply must be valid, executable R code only...</i></p> <p>Example output</p> <pre>n1 count_fas <- adsl %>% dplyr::filter(FASFL == "Y") %>% dplyr::summarise(n = dplyr::n_distinct(USUBJID)) print(count_fas) n2 df_os <- dplyr::filter(adeffte, PARAM == "Overall Survival (months)") df_join <- dplyr::inner_join(df_os, dplyr::select(adsl, USUBJID, FASFL), by = "USUBJID") df_sub <- dplyr::filter(df_join, FASFL == "Y") df_ev <- dplyr::mutate(df_sub, event = 1 - CNSR) fit <- survival::survfit(survival::Surv(AVAL, event) ~ 1, data = df_ev) print(list(fit = fit, summary = summary(fit))) ...</pre>	<p>Important notes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each agent has access to the detailed trial metadata, including variable names, labels, and possible cell values. • Each R script generated by the Virtual Team is safely executed on patient-level data within a protected evaluation framework that automatically corrects and re-runs code after errors, ensuring uninterrupted generation of complete summary reports.

Note:

SCE, Statistical Computing Environment.

The summary report is based on synthetic data.

Figure 3. Evaluation of the AI Virtual Team using the same starting prompt and ten repeats

Note:

The starting prompt (“Summarize the dataset focusing on findings that are clinically meaningful.”) was applied using the GPT-5 model on a data package including four ADaM datasets (ADSL, ADRS, ADTTE, ADAE). For each of ten repeated runs, the AI Virtual Team performed ten analyses and generated a 200-word report.

(A) Across all 100 analyses, accurate executable statistical code was produced; four analyses required a second code-generation attempt.

(B) Across the ten runs, 117 unique analytical results were identified and included in the ten reports. The median number of analytical results per report was 39. Some results appeared in all ten reports (N=10 on x-axis), whereas many appeared only once or a few times. N = 8 is absent from the horizontal axis because no analytical result was observed in exactly eight reports.